

EDUCATION, HEALTH AND WASTE MANAGEMENT PRACTICES OF AN EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTION: KISS (KALINGA INSTITUTE OF SOCIAL SCIENCES) AS AN UNIQUE MODEL FOR TRIBAL'S IN THE PRESENT EDUCATION SECTOR

Lakshmipriya Malla

Assistant Professor, KIIT School of Social Sciences,
(KISS) Bhubaneswar, Odisha, India

Abstract:

The present study aimed to assess the education, health and waste management practices of Kalinga Institute of Social Sciences (KISS-A home for 25,000 disadvantaged groups of children)) at present for tribal students of whole world. Specifically, it determined the level of effectiveness of education and skill, health awareness and Waste Management Practices of tribal students in terms of: inculcation of skills, practice of healthy life and collection strategies, disposal and recovery and processing of waste materials within the campus by the most vulnerable group of students of our country. In the same time here highlighted the institution invented unique model of providing education and skill, health awareness and waste management to the tribal students of globe. This research utilized descriptive survey method of research. To prove the above objectives three research questions were established and focus of the questions ware to examine different vocational trade practices and its significance in the present day context to achieve MDGs and how far making them self-reliance after education. Also make an attempt to highlight the health and waste management practices of the institution are the key thrust of the questions. The qualitative methodology (Interviews, documents analysis and observation) are used. Findings show that it is one of the best international models of practice to achieve MDGs. Like: Eradicating extreme poverty and hunger, Achieving universal primary education, Improving mental health and Combating HIV/AIDS, malaria and other diseases. It is also found that, it is helping the students for making them self-reliant after completion of their education and meet the basic requirements and improved their economic condition, health practices and reuse techniques of local waste materials which will definitely leads to achieve MDGs. The

researchers also concluded that waste management practices of KISS is effective in terms of collection, disposable, recovery and processing as perceived by the respondents.

Keywords: education, health, waste management, KISS, tribal's, unique model and MDGs

1. Introduction

Kalinga Institute of Social Sciences is the largest tribal residential institution where there are 25000 children from 62 tribes, and 60 per cent of them are tribal girls. The campus sprawls out over 80 acres and the built up area is a whopping 10,00,000 square feet. The library alone occupies 15,000 square feet and holds over more than 30,000 titles. This makes it the largest residential tribal institution in the world. KISS provides accommodation, food, healthcare, education, vocational training absolutely free in the aim of achieving millennium development goals (MDGs). To top this, there is job assurance once the education is complete. It is one of the role model and front runner in the modern education age to implement and integrate the new and innovative vocational ideas along with waste management techniques in the institution which leads to arrest problems in the path of MDGs fixed by world. According to Perez, (2011) segregating the waste is also doing part in waste management. Avoidance of having trash is one way of lessening the garbage problem in the country. Using materials that are environmental friendly, to minimize and solve the garbage problems of the Philippines. On the other side, the focus on economic growth has led as to take environmental management for granted. Solid waste became the most visible environmental problem in the country, and has remained so for years.

A management to that can help planners study objectively and make rational decisions as to the best alternative strategic options of managing, recovering and utilizing the vast quantity of solid waste is a very important investment (Guzman, et.al 2010).

With connecting to the above review at KISS the role of education in facilitating social and economic progress along with health and waste management has long been recognized not only in the country's education system but also by the UNO council. At KISS education improves functional and analytical ability of the tribal students and thereby opens up opportunities for individuals and also groups to achieve greater access to labor markets, health healthy practices, reuse of waste material to improve

economy and livelihoods of the tribal which helps them to be a part of mainstream. A better educated labor force and proper management of local waste material is essential if we are to meet the labor supply requirements of faster growth. So here education is not only an instrument of enhancing efficiency but is also an effective tool of widening and augmenting democratic participation and upgrading the overall quality of individual and societal life.

Although Prof. Samanta Sir establishes the institution with best modern amenities and make the campus Wi-Fi, but the mission of him to provide education to the child only to be a good human being in life, so one notable saying of him i.e. *"Krutangya Hua, Krutaghna Hua nahin" "Be grateful, not ungrateful"* to his students and society and also he preached it throughout globe. His mission to provide education to child only to serve the purpose of human life, so he emphasized value education, life skill education and spiritual enlightened topic to students in the school only to facilitate the Govt. aims of achieving Millennium Development Goals (MDGs). Along with above holy thinking he has also many missions to provide the proper health and hygiene practice by the tribal and proper use of local material to improve their economy.

Skills and knowledge are the engines of economic growth and social development of any country. Countries with higher and better levels of knowledge and skills respond more effectively and promptly to challenges and opportunities of globalization. India is in transition to a knowledge based economy and its competitive edge will be determined by the abilities of its people to create, share and use knowledge more effectively which is emphasized in KISS and provided the skills and competencies accordingly to the most disadvantaged group of students only because of solving the problem of Govt. in the way of MDGs achievement *Like: Eradicating extreme poverty and hunger, Achieving universal primary education, Improving mental health and Combating HIV/AIDS, malaria and other diseases.* This transition will require India to develop workers (especially rural tribal areas people) into knowledge workers who will be more flexible, analytical, and adaptable and multi skilled along with proper hygienic and life skilled. In the new knowledge economy, the skill sets will include professional, managerial, operational, and behavioral, inter personal and inter functional skills.

As education is, the means for bringing socio-economic transformation in a society also have the ability to eradicate all the hindrances in the path of MDGs and finally achieve all in the one time, so various measures are being taken to enhance the access of education to the marginalized sections of the society at KISS. In this juncture, KISS is really fulfilling the aims of our country through education with integrating vocational skills, health practices and proper waste material use training. To achieve

these goals, India needs flexible education and training system that will provide the foundation for learning, secondary and tertiary education, and to develop required competencies as means of achieving lifelong learning, which is now already practicing in the institution.

Review of related literature

We can better understand the importance of integration of skills in the school education, health practices and waste management with the following literature which is already proved by many researchers like: World Bank (2010) India's labour force makes up about 39 per cent of the total population. According to the World Bank, the Indian labour market in the 1990s was better, despite acceleration in job growth in subsequent years. These conclusions are based on three main facts: (i) a comparison of job growth over two decades – that is, 1983–1994 and 1994–2005 – suggests that job growth was flat at 2 per cent over the long term; (ii) the spurt in employment since 2000 has been accompanied by a marked deceleration in real wage growth and even a decline for many workers, implying that the number of working poor has increased in the past five years; and (iii) low-paying, relatively unproductive, informal sector jobs continue to dominate the labour market. Lauglo, (2004): In the context of school education, we need to consider adapting the currently academic-focused curricula to embrace vocational or practical subjects – “vocationalisation” – so that students have more options but we must do so without closing the doors to traditional academic options. Msisika, (1994): in which he argued that vocationalisation should not be relied upon as a solution to youth unemployment, and that the costs of such a programme could be difficult to justify in a relatively poor country such as Malawi. He also expressed concern that job markets can change rapidly and without warning, and that this makes it impossible for schools to fully prepare – that is, train – their students for the world of work. In short, in his opinion vocational training is a specialist area that should be undertaken by specialist institutions rather than by general education institutions. Furto and Paz (2013): The residents of Batangas City encountered problems in the implementation of Solid Waste Management practices to a moderate level such as lack of awareness regarding the effects of solid waste management to health, lack of training on proper solid waste management practices, public indifference, increasing population and inadequate government policies. In the same way that municipal waste characterization studies provide local decision makers with a detailed understanding of a waste stream and enable waste management programs to be tailored to local needs.

Chang and Davila, 2008: waste characterization studies at colleges and universities identify campus specific and regionally relevant opportunities for waste reduction and recycling, representing an essential step towards greening the campus Keniry, 1995; Creighton, 1998. When carefully planned, campus waste characterization studies are relatively inexpensive and can generate administrative support, cooperation among students, faculty and staff and inspire further involvement in campus sustainability issues. Bradly et al., 1999; Eagles and Demare, 1999: Environmental attitude of young people appears to be crucial as they ultimately play a direct role in providing knowledge-based solutions to in-coming environmental problem. Evans et al., 1996; Ballantyne, 1998; Gallagher et al., 2000: School environmental programs, although addressed to students if properly channel can also influence the environmental knowledge, attitude and behaviour of adults (parents, teachers and local community members) through the process of intergenerational influence.

Rationale of the study

While high-quality pre-primary, primary, secondary, higher and vocational education and training are basic necessity to a country's success in the present day context, in a rapidly changing world lifelong learning and Millennium Development Goals are now national priority as well as it is one of the primary goal of KISS because it is the key to continued employment, entrepreneurship, health and hygiene and skill of waste management in general and tribal group of child in particular to facilities MDGs and participate fully in society as empowered citizens. Vocational education, health and waste management are therefore crucial to the KISS broader education agenda and essential to the development of a knowledge society, economy and democracy of the tribal people to leave a healthy and peaceful life.

Let us therefore consider the outcome of vocational skills training, health education and waste management strategies that we are focusing on today at KISS which is to empowering particularly tribal citizens with providing the new light to achieve Millennium Development Goals. A citizen's life is not lived in isolation but in the midst of society, which unhappily is unequal if we critically analyse the real scenario of tribal's in our country and state that the lack of decent employment opportunities, many diseases and waste of many food materials forces youth to take up miserable self-employment and low paid contractual jobs with deplorable working conditions. So here one of the front runner providing proper vocational skills along with proper blending of academic subjects to disseminate knowledge of proper use of

local wastage and proper practice of health and hygiene to the tribal's need to be analysis in front of the educated masses which will definitely help the policy maker to start this type of model which will enable the students of our country in a long run to achieve our fixed MDGs and make their life happy with eradicating malnutrition, illiteracy, hunger, poverty etc. So here, the following issues are in hand for the discussion.

Issues in Hand

Following are the issues or research questions upon which the analysis will be based on:

1. Whether the integrated academic curricula of KISS solving the pre-fixed objectives for tribal, which leads to achieve MDGs?
2. What are the diversified skills those inculcated within the tribal students?
3. Whether the integrated curricula have any impact on their health and hygiene and capability of reusing local waste material or capable to achieve Millennium Development Goals with eradicating hindrances?

Objectives of the study

The present study addressed with the following objectives:

1. To study the integrated academic curricula of KISS and its worth for the tribal's in particular reference to achieve MDGs.
2. To highlight diversified vocational skills inculcated at KISS within the students.
3. To examine the health programme and its impact on the tribal children after education and how enable them to live one healthy diseases free life.
4. To highlight the campus and waste management programmes

Methodology of the study

Methodology

Descriptive survey method used in the study as the investigators tried to get information about more than one variable also with better understanding of perceptions of stakeholders (Hittleman and Simon, 1997). Through this method information about conditions, situations and events that occur in the present can be obtained (UNESCO, 2005). Therefore, in the present study the investigator used this method to explore all possibilities to highlight, measure the impact and effectiveness of integration curricula

of KISS and its different health related and waste management programmers with regarding to the tribal up-liftment and better education, Also the problems and its eradication from the root to achieve Millennium Development Goals.

Secondary data collection

The sources of secondary data are the published and unpublished reports. Data from secondary sources were gathered from books, articles, journals, published reports, and Government documents. Quantitative information collected with regard to current impact, issues on integrated curriculum, also regarding MDGs. In the same time highlighted health and waste management programmes on tribal education and better life along with their economic development.

Discussion

Integrated academic curricula of KISS Vs. its worth for the tribal's in particular reference to achieve MDGs.

Indigenous tribal people make up around 370 million of the world's population; they constitute around one third of the world's 900 million extremely rural poor people. Everyday indigenous all over the world face issues of violence and brutality due to their economic insufficiency, health related problems like malaria/HIV/AIDS etc., and the wastage of local materials which impacts of our large scale development. As far as Odisha is concerned, indigenous people constitute 22.13 percent of Odisha's population, where chronic poverty, severe poverty and multidimensional deprivation characterize several parts. The Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation, Government of India, has brought out the 'Millennium Development Goals—India Country Report 2011', which shows India's performance with regard to the MDGs, and projects the likely achievement rates by 2015.

Consequently a discourse on these issues becomes pertinent at this particular juncture, so here according to the above problem the institution tried to solve the issues like Skill development, proper practice of health related issues, proper use of waste materials mixed etc. The intense focus of KISS on raising academic standards, increasing high school graduation requirements, and improving post-secondary completion rates indicates that schools and side by side providing one of the interested vocational skill, proper health practices and awareness regarding waste management which will help himself for self-reliance in future with eradicating poverty, malnutrition, illiteracy, child mortality etc. from their life.

Providing a program of integrated academic and vocational curriculum where education, health and waste management are the primary focus and promising alternative to both teachers and tribal students. Another objective of blending the present curriculum is in a highly competitive, multicultural workplace, integrated skills and personal qualities are in great demand. Along with the above objectives following are some of the major areas which the institution wants to arrest from the tribal areas through the proper blended curriculum:-

Inadequate Poverty Reduction

How far have the SCs and STs progressed towards attaining the MDGs? The available official statistics show a gradual progress towards the attainment of many MDGs including in the case of SCs and STs. However, there is a big gap in the levels of development between the SCs–STs and other social groups. The STs have the highest incidence of poverty at 32.5 per cent, in 2009–10, so KISS provides the skill and proper blended education to make them self-sufficient in their life for adequate poverty reduction.

Increase in Inequality

What is the implication of these rising inequalities for SCs and STs? A large proportion of the SCs and STs are not able to partake of their share in the 'shining' sectors—those characterized by high growth—of India, which employ about 31 per cent of all workers. Only 5.2 per cent of the total SC–ST workers are benefitting from this 'shining' part of India. Similarly, the enrolment ratio is the lowest and the dropout rate highest in the lowest quintile groups. Both the SCs and STs together form a large percentage of the population belonging to the lower quintile groups, but at KISS there is 100% enrolment and 100% retention and providing best educative model for tribal's and their upliftment.

Malnutrition

Despite significant progress in economic growth, India has a widespread incidence of malnutrition among children below the age of five years—about 42 per cent among them are underweight and nearly 59 per cent are stunted. The incidence of malnutrition is the highest among STs (54.5 per cent), followed by SCs (47.9 per cent), and other social groups (36.3 per cent). In the same time the average annual rate of reduction in malnutrition was the lowest for STs (0.37 per cent), in this juncture KISS not only

eradicating malnutrition with providing economic sufficiency and awareness regarding this issues but changing their previous life style and culture.

Lack of Universal Primary Education

However, these encouraging developments in enrolment have also been accompanied by a huge drop-out rate among children due to various reasons. The reasons for drop-out among the marginalized students largely include the poor financial conditions of their parents and their disinterest in studies, but here KISS provides education along with technical and vocational training absolutely free within the campus with best infrastructure such as adequate classrooms and separate toilets for girl students, along with poor teaching resources are the other problems that lead to higher drop-out rates.

Gender Parity

While the SCs and STs are very close to others in attaining gender parity in terms of net attendance in primary education, the issue remains worrisome at the secondary level of education. This could be because for them the distance to the education facility from their places of residence poses a major hindrance, which discourages girls from continuing their higher education. Thus, the major concern here for a new development paradigm like KISS education model, which provides above everything with the hand of tribal is needed to universalize secondary education and improve its quality in order to ensure gender parity.

Infant Mortality

With an infant mortality rate (IMR) of 47 per 1000 live births in 2010, India is unlikely to attain its target of 26.7 by 2015, despite achieving a significant improvement in the IMR over the period 2000–10. The high IMR among SCs and STs is generally attributed to various factors including their poverty, high incidence of malnutrition, lack of health facilities in the SC–ST-dominated areas and poor public health service delivery. Moreover, the available evidence suggests the persistence of discrimination in the delivery of nutrition support services to the marginalized groups, with relating these problems in grassroots level KISS started the skill development programme, life skill education, vocational education etc. which really help them to come out from these problems.

Child Immunization

With 74 per cent of the children in the age group of 12–23 months in 2009 having been immunized against measles, India has made remarkable progress in the area of child immunization. However, the country is still likely to miss the MDG target of 100 per cent immunization by 2015 the ratio was less than the national average by 4 percentage points. There is also a huge inter-state variability, with less than one-third of the children having been vaccinated in Orissa as compared to 70 per cent in Uttarakhand during 2011. So KISS opened her own dispensary for immunization and arranging awareness programme by these students in their own areas to overcome this problem in tribal areas.

Access to Safe Drinking Water and Sanitation

Access to safe drinking water is crucial as it prevents water-borne diseases and consequently high morbidity. While there has been a considerable improvement in access to safe drinking water, still over one-third of the ST households and nearly one-fourth of the SC and Other households do not have such access as per the 2011 Population Census. Thus, the situation of STs with regard to this indicator is far worse than the national average. To combat this problem KISS first of all arranged mineral drinking water for the campus 25,000 tribal students along with providing them the well sanitation awareness and practices in their life.

Integrated academic curricula of KISS vs. diversified skills inculcated to tribals

India needs to train 70 million people in vocational skills over the next five years. In addition, there is a need to retrain another 360 million workers. The government's target is to train 500 million people by 2022, also by encouraging the participation of entrepreneurs and private organizations. The target is high. The workability of the structure that India has developed would depend on the capacity of the people who are responsible for reaching the objectives. Efforts over the past few years have not yielded satisfactory results with regard to the achievement of the objective in a defined period. Against the background of a huge gap between skills demand and supply, India has taken the initiative to develop a system of vocational training.

With keeping in view of the above need here emphasized following need based vocational various trades according to the need and interest of the students as well as current society. KISS introduces a large scale and different vocational based education like:

- I. Computer Training
- II. Composite Farming
- III. Food Processing
- IV. Animal Husbandry
- V. Art and Craft
- VI. Tailoring
- VII. Appliqué
- VIII. Making soft toys
- IX. Chemical works (phenyl, hand wash, dish wash etc.)
- X. Recycle Paper
- XI. Painting
- XII. Photo Framing
- XIII. Incense Sticks
- XIV. Food processing and preservation
- XV. Medical Attendant
- XVI. Security Guard Training
- XVII. Bakery
- XVIII. Pisciculture
- XIX. Driving
- XX. Mineral water processing

With a huge scale with the principle like at least one vocational course is necessary for everyone. KISS introduces different vocational education because vocational education link with productivity economic development and individual productivity. It is designed to impart necessary occupation skills among the tribal student to mould them in to successful and make them fit in to job market along with prove themselves one of the major stake holder in the process of national development. Also, one of the main aims of this institution is that when the completion of the study they involved in any vocation for the maintaining livelihood.

Integrated academic curricula of KISS Vs. Health programme for healthy diseases free life

In the year 2000 from several studies UNFPA found out that Worldwide, adolescent females and males are reaching puberty sooner, marrying later and having more premarital sex. One third women worldwide give birth before the age of 20, with deliveries by women under 20 totaling 15 million annually. Pregnant adolescents are at risk of morbidity and mortality because of problems and complications during

pregnancy and child birth. Five million adolescents between the ages of 15 to 19 have unsafe abortions every year. 70,000 abortion related deaths occur among the adolescents each year. Again the findings also provided evidences that half of HIV infections occur in 15 to 24 years old and one third of new cases of curable sexually transmitted infections affect people younger than 25. Adolescents cover 29 percent of the total population in developing countries and about 32 percent in least developed countries. This creates an alarming call for health interventions that are flexible, conducive and responsive to the unavoidable needs of people coming under this age group.

ARSH is identified as a key strategy under the Reproductive and Child Health Phase-II (RCH-II) program and National Rural Health Mission. In order to achieve this mission different organizations involved in this intervention have been developing and using several media and means keeping an eye on the contemporary issues. IEC materials are one of these communication media widely used and liked by the target group. It is seen through many researches that these materials have proved their role and their contributions more significantly in the field of Health Education and Health Awareness programs.

Kalinga Institute of Social Sciences (KISS) in association with UNFPA is imparting Life Skill based Adolescent Reproductive Health Education to nearly 25,000 tribal students since 2009. Life Skills based Sexual and Reproductive Health Education for adolescents started in KISS in the year 2009 in partnership with UNFPA with two broad objectives.

1. The enhancement of knowledge and life skills among the tribal students studying in KISS.
2. Building capacity of KISS as a resource center to support and expand life skills education and broaden research base in area of Adolescent Reproductive Sexual Health.

Keeping an eye on these objectives Programme Management Unit developed some culture sensitive resource and communication tools with the help of-trained resource persons of KISS, - a state level ethical committee

During 2012, 2013 and 2014 LSE and SRH intervention moved beyond the boundaries of KISS and now it covers 318 tribal residential schools, 182 KGBVs of Odisha and almost 70,000 children of these schools. Now the interesting impact of this successful programme is there is fully awareness between the 70,000 students and their family regarding common diseases and the teenage pregnancy is near about totally arrested within the areas.

Campus and waste management programmes vs. tribal awareness

In the campus there are many programmes undertaken for waste management and recycling of wastages. Some of are described here like:

Biogas

In the campus, more than 25,000 students are residing and taking everything free, so it is obvious when 25,000 students taking their mean much food will be waste. So here to manage that wastage food one biogas established and use the wastage food and created gas, this gas is using for mechanized kitchen system for cooking purposes.

Garden and landscaping

Organic waste from garden and landscaping activities is composted, and the resultant material is used to improve the soil quality within the KISS compound and the plant nursery. Composting heaps are located near the sports arena and at Jagannath temple. Normally the garden and landscaping activities produces green waste every day. But these are using successfully and making the whole compound of KISS beautiful.

Clinic

The cleaning personnel from KISS collect office rubbish from the clinic. Clinical waste is collected in special plastic bags while sharp clinical objects (syringes, etc.) are collected in small plastic containers. The KISS cleaner collects all clinical waste once or twice per month, depending on the quantity generated. This homemade incinerator has no equipment for controlling temperature and reducing the discharge of gases or particles to the air (i.e. through the use of filters). The incineration of medical waste potentially results in the emission of carcinogenic gases, such as dioxins and furans.

Toilets

In between the KISS campus near about 1000 toilets for the students, those are used in daily basis, so cleaning Staff members from the KISS collect sanitary waste from the washrooms. They have many rubbish containers on the compound, which are emptied daily. The waste is taken to the unused area where it is incinerated (using the same incinerator that burns medical waste from the clinic).

Findings of the study

Following are the major findings of the study:

1. The students act pragmatically in accordance to the motivation they receive from the programme and other staff of their educational system.
2. Here at KISS which Vocational Education provided to the tribal's is not merely training, but the development of abilities in order to articulate, mobilize and put knowledge contents, skills and values into action for their betterment of their life.
3. After the education they are getting better employment prospects and increased ability to retain the current job and opportunities.
4. One of the interesting finding of the study that it reductions in crime in the areas, as we know many crimes are occurring in the tribal areas due to their economic insufficiency and literacy, so it's obvious to reduce the level of crime in the areas.
5. It develop the health practices among the tribal's after their economic and literacy change
6. The waste management programmes are using here at large scale and also the influence upon the tribal students and they are also using this recycling model in their areas.

Measure to be taken for prosperity of schedule tribes for achieving MDGs

Many programmes helped tribal to improve their conditions. The following are important for further improvement.

1. Strict implementation of reservation of seats in all sectors of employment
2. Proper looking into reservation of seats in institutions like particularly public primary and secondary schools according to the Right to education (Article 21(A)) also at the higher learning,
3. Destroy of their habitations and culture should be reduced in their dominated areas because major projects, SEZs and other projects are causing for migration of ST's which is now a major problem in the field of our economic development, and these issues are also responsible for their health problem.
4. Proper plan and programmes should be there by the government along with proper awareness programmes for local waste management in the remote tribal areas of our country.
5. Development of forest and villages where all the facilities will be available like school, public health centre with all amenities along with all necessary government offices are needed for Tribal prosperity
6. Proper rules along with proper execution along with inspection for the waste of the industry in these areas, which creates many diseases in those areas.

7. Along with above following some useful strategies should be there for proper waste management which is already used in KISS like:

Solid Waste Management Strategies

- Waste management as a part of school curriculum;
- Student groups;
- Awareness trainings for schools children & teachers;
- School Activities – songs, games, quiz, involving children in segregation activities
- Awareness campaigns in the neighbourhood; and
- Involving children & their parents.

Also the school should take the responsibility of these issues as KISS implemented it successfully the programmes may be:

Solid Waste Management Strategies – at school level

- Integrated approach
- Administrative interventions
- New approach for waste management
- Regulations & their implementation.

Conclusion

In conclusion, vocational technical education systems are dynamic in nature. The challenges and opportunities are unique. The key issue today is how to build a responsive vocational system in time for the future. While there are more differences than similarities, the overall educational goals, concerns and issues are the same.

However, from an international perspective, there is no one ideal system that will suit the needs or aspirations of all countries. The systems are often shaped by the economic, social and cultural conditions of the local community. *“Education is the key to development, then vocational training is the master key that will open the doors to employment opportunities, sustainable livelihoods and self-reliance—and close the doors to adversities”.*

Vocational Courses have already been offered in several secondary schools as a pilot test although not consistently across the India. There is a continuing need for all people or stakeholders to collaborate in introducing quality vocational training programmes in secondary schools across the region. Collaboration is needed between the countries that are in the process of strengthening these programmes and countries that are already running successful TVET courses in their secondary schools like KISS.

References

1. Ballantyne R (1998). Interpreting 'visions': Addressing environmental education goals through interpretation. In: D. Uzzell and R Ballantyne (Eds) *Contemporary Issues in Heritage and Environ.* Interpr. Pp. 9-77.
2. Bradley CJ, Waliczek TM, Zajicek JM (1999). Relationship between environmental knowledge and environmental attitude of high school students. *J. Environ. Edu.* 30(3): 17-21.
3. Chang N, Davila E. Municipal solid waste characterization and management strategies for the Lower Rio Valley, Texas. *Waste Manage* 2008;28:776–94. Ching R, Gogan R. Campus recycling: everyone plays a part. *New Dir Higher Educ* 1992;77:113–25.
4. Creighton S. *Greening the Ivory Tower: improving the environmental track record of universities, colleges, and other institutions.* Cambridge, MA: The MIT Press; 1998.
5. Eagles PFJ, Demare R (1999). Factors influencing children' environmental attitudes. *J. Environ. Edu.* 30(4): Pp. 33.
6. Evans SM, Gill ME, Marchant J (1996). School children as educators: The indirect influence of environmental education in schools on parents' attitude towards the environment.
7. J. Furto M., Reyes P. (2013). Greening of the Solid Waste Management in Batangas City, *Journal of Energy Technologies and Policy*, 3(11), 187-194
8. Gallagher J, Wheeler C, McDonough M, Namfa B (2000). Sustainable environmental education for a sustainable environment: lessons of Thailand for other nations. *Walter Air Soil Pollut.* 123(1-4): 489- 503.
9. Guzman J., Paningbatan E., &Alcantara A. (2010). A Geographic Information System-Based Decision Support System for Solid Waste Recovery and Utilization in Tuguegarao City, Cagayan, Philippines. *Journal of Environmental Science and Management*, 13(1): 52-66.
10. Hittleman, D. R. And Simon, A. J. (1997), *Interpreting Educational Research: An Introduction for Consumers of Research*, Prentice-Hall, Inc. New Jersey.
11. Keniry J. *Ecodemia: campus environmental stewardship at the turn of the 21st century.* Washington, DC, USA: National Wildlife Federation; 1995.
12. Lauglo, Jon. (2004). *Vocationalized secondary education revisited [draft paper].* Available at:
http://siteresources.worldbank.org/INTAFRREGTOPSEIA/Resources/paper_Lauglo.pdf

13. Msiska, F. G. W. (1994). Some practical limits of curriculum vocationalization as a remedy to school leavers' unemployment: Focus on Malawi. *International Review of Education/Internationale Zeitschrift für Erziehungswissenschaft/ Revue Internationale de l'Education*, 40(2), 135-148.
14. Perez D. (2011) *Spectrum Blue Steel* (December 8, 2013) *Practical Action Nepal* (November 2008) *Best Practices on Solid Waste Management of Nepalese Cities*
15. UNESCO (2005), *Quantitative Research Methods in Educational Planning*, UNESCO International Institute for Educational Planning, Paris, France.
16. World Bank (2010) *India's Employment Challenge – Creating Jobs, Helping Workers*. New Delhi: Oxford University Press.

Creative Commons licensing terms

Authors will retain the copyright of their published articles agreeing that a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0) terms will be applied to their work. Under the terms of this license, no permission is required from the author(s) or publisher for members of the community to copy, distribute, transmit or adapt the article content, providing a proper, prominent and unambiguous attribution to the authors in a manner that makes clear that the materials are being reused under permission of a Creative Commons License. Views, opinions and conclusions expressed in this research article are views, opinions and conclusions of the author(s). Open Access Publishing Group and European Journal of Open Education and E-learning Studies shall not be responsible or answerable for any loss, damage or liability caused in relation to/arising out of conflict of interests, copyright violations and inappropriate or inaccurate use of any kind content related or integrated on the research work. All the published works are meeting the Open Access Publishing requirements and can be freely accessed, shared, modified, distributed and used in educational, commercial and non-commercial purposes under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License \(CC BY 4.0\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).